

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable 8.5

Protocol for the collection of research results

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union

1. Executive Summary

Task 8.4 Disseminate & Promote, involves the dissemination and promotion of scientific evidence based outcomes for sustainable soil futures as a result of both the existing and newly developed knowledge within the EJP SOIL Programme. This task aims to capture research results relevant to policy and make them available to policymakers at national, regional, European and international levels.

Before these key findings can be shared, they must first be collected. This activity occurs in Sub-Task 8.4.1 Information Capture, which involved the development of a protocol for rapid collection of research results which could be of interest to policymakers. This Deliverable 8.5 Protocol for the collection of research results, describes the protocol developed under Sub-Task 8.4.1. It presents the method of data collection developed and outlines the metadata and input categories of information to be collected. The protocol itself consists of a total of 46 questions within eight sections developed in a MS Excel data collection template.

The protocol aims to capture information about the research projects occurring within the EJP SOIL and their findings in such a way as to present a comprehensive snapshot of the completed or ongoing work and the relevance of that work to various areas of policy, stakeholders and policymakers at different levels (national, regional, EU, International). This will contribute to the subsequent creation of portal containing all of the collected data on the EJP SOIL website.

The protocol will be completed by EJP SOIL participants who should review their project load and fill in this form for all of the relevant ongoing projects they are currently working on. It is suggested that this review and protocol completion occur bi-annually to capture new projects that arise throughout the course of the EJP SOIL Programme lifetime.

Keeping in mind the users of the protocol as well as the long-term aim of dissemination of the key information sought by policy stakeholders by EJP SOIL WP9 “Dissemination” in subsequent tasks, this protocol was developed with consultation from WP9. It was determined that a MS Excel data collection template was best suited to the needs of data summary and dissemination activities. Other criteria including the nature of data input types, the flexibility and customizability for data management and reporting as well as a high degree of user familiarity with this program also contributed to the suitability of MS Excel for this task.

The eight sections of the protocol collect data on a range of relevant aspects of the research project including background information, methods used, the accessibility of the results, possible implications, relevance to the EJP SOIL Programme and potential policy recommendations and relatedness of results to policymakers. Images of each section of the protocol in the MS Excel data collection template are included in the Appendix. This deliverable has also been submitted with a copy of the MS Excel file itself.

The creation of this protocol and the subsequent collection of data will set the foundation for the development of the Resources Infrastructure and Capabilities Inventory (RICI) and the ensuing creation of a useful database that can be utilised in future EJP SOIL tasks and shared with the relevant parties in the future. It will improve the transfer of knowledge from scientific outputs to the policy domain and increase the access to available results and knowledge for policymakers at all levels. This will also increase the visibility of the work of the EJP SOIL Programme at an international level so that the EJP SOIL can become the leading source of scientific outputs and evidence based advice on optimising agricultural soil management.

2. Introduction

The science to policy interface is often a topic of much critical discussion by scientists and policymakers alike, and the importance of protocols and tools for collating scientific data, outputs and recommendations that meet the needs of both parties and allows for effective communication and exchange of key information is critical for transferring the knowledge being done by the EJP SOIL. Such a protocol will help to bridge the knowledge transfer gap between the scientific information and results generated from the projects within the EJP SOIL and the policymakers who consider such scientific evidence essential to the development, implementation, monitoring, verification and reporting cycles for new and existing soil related policy. This report describes the EJP SOIL protocol for collection of research results. The information collected using this protocol will contribute to a database of research findings and recommendations from research projects and reports from stocktaking exercises and stakeholder engagement. These research findings, collated over the duration of the EJP SOIL, will be made available to policymakers via an online portal on the EJP SOIL website and through policy maker forums and workshops.

This protocol describes a structured methodology for the collection of new knowledge, key outcomes and syntheses generated from work done within EJP SOIL WP 2-7 and funded projects. This protocol and the method of data collection and summary were chosen to enable dissemination of the key information sought by policy stakeholders by EJP SOIL WP9 “Dissemination” in subsequent tasks. A MS Excel data collection template was determined as the most efficient platform considering criteria such as the nature of data input types and the flexibility and customizability for data management and reporting. There is also a high degree of user familiarity with this program among the relevant parties.

When developing the protocol special consideration was given to the understanding and elucidation of those aspects of research most relevant to policy makers and linkages within the wider the EJP SOIL. As such, data is collected not only on the methods and results involved in the research but also on the potential relevant areas of policy, the potential stakeholders targeted by the research and the relevant EJP SOIL domains and impact areas.

3. Protocol Methodology

This protocol for the collection of research results relevant to policy makers has been designed for use by the EJP SOIL programme and its partners. An overview of the protocol is presented in this report, and the MS Excel tool developed and formatted for the collection of the data/results (shown in Annex 1, Appendix). The protocol consists of seven sections outlined here in detail. Prior to data collection an introduction including the aim of this protocol and general instructions for inputting research results is provided for the user. Following this, each section of the protocol is introduced. These sections are as follows:

1. Research Project Summary Overview
2. General Information
3. Background
4. Methods
5. Results
6. Relevance to the EJP SOIL
7. Relevance to Policymakers

Within each section the questions, the format of the responses required and in some cases standardised response options i.e. dropdown lists or checkboxes, are provided. Each question has a response in the format of one of the following:

1. An open-ended text box
2. A predetermined list of answers from which multiple options can be chosen
3. A predetermined list of answers from which only one option can be chosen

In all cases where there is a predetermined list of response options, those options are clearly stated within the relevant tables in this report.

The resulting protocol outline was then used to design the Excel file and Word Document. Special attention was given to the formatting of the MS Excel template to help engagement with the users and allow for the easy completion of the relevant questions. A simple user interface, with innate visual prompts was used to ensure that the response completion flowed in a logical and natural order, limiting the tedium for end users. The initial draft protocol was developed by WP 8 in consultation with WP 9, following which the protocol was shared with the EJP SOIL partners to get feedback and further ideas to help optimise the template and protocol. It is suggested that EJP SOIL participants review their project load and complete this form bi-annually for any new projects for which the form has not been already completed.

3.1. Research Project Summary Overview

This section will provide basic information about the research project as a feedback to a possible initial search result. It aims to help end-users select projects that could be relevant to their search.

Table 1 Metadata required for the summary overview section of the protocol.

Input Category	Input Criteria
Project Title	Open-ended response, text
Abstract/ Summary	Open-ended response, text
Key Takeaways	Open-ended response, text
Keywords	Open-ended response, text

3.2. General Information

This section collects information on those involved and the aims of the research/ study.

Table 2 Metadata required for the general information section of the protocol

Input Category	Input Criteria
Project coordinator/Lead partner	Open-ended response, text
Contact person/ Reference email	Open-ended response, text
Project partners	Open-ended response, text
Project Objectives	Open-ended response, text
Official project website	Open-ended response, text
Project Status	Open-ended response, text
Duration of Project	Open-ended response, text
Source of Funding	Open-ended response, text

3.3. Background

Information gathered in this section provides the context of the research/ study conducted as well as specific information that may be relevant.

Table 3 Metadata required for the background section of the protocol

Input Category	Input Criteria	Input Options
Target (or Beneficiary) Country (s)	Open-ended response, text	
EU Climatic Zone(s)	Open-ended response, text	
Scale of Project	Predetermined options, drop down list, searchable	Local, Regional, National, European, Global
Land Use Type	Predetermined options, multiple choices possible, drop down list, searchable	Arable land, Fallow, Forest, Permanent pasture, Permanent meadow, Other
If other please specify	Open-ended response, text	
Soil Type	Predetermined options, drop down list, searchable	Mineral, Organic
WRB Soil Great Group	Predetermined options, multiple choices possible, drop down list, searchable	Acrisols, Alisols, Andosols, Anthrosols, Arenosols, Calcisols, Cambisols, Chernozems, Cryosols, Durisols, Ferralsols, Fluvisols, Gleysols, Gypsisols, Histosols, Kastanozems, Leptosols, Lixisols, Luvisols, Nitisols, Phaeozems, Planosols, Plinthosols, Podzols, Solonchaks, Solonetz, Stagnosols, Technosols, Umbrisol, Vertisols
Please specify soil type	Open-ended response, text	
Soil Drainage Class	Predetermined options, drop down list, searchable	Excessively drained, Somewhat excessively drained, Well drained, Moderately well drained, Somewhat poorly drained, Poorly drained, Very poorly drained, Not Relevant
Please specify local soil drainage class		
Comments/ Clarifications	Open-ended response, text	Opportunity for projects to elaborate on their background

3.4. Methods

This section will provide information on the approach/methodology used to carry out the research, and the parameters measured and the indicators and the units used. For each category of parameters it is possible in the Excel sheet to enter multiple parameters and go on to define the value range, units and indicators related to each parameter (Fig. 4, Appendix).

Table 4 Metadata required for the methods section of the protocol

Input Category	Input Criteria	Input Options
Method of data collection	Predetermined options, drop down list, searchable	Empirical data, Secondary data
Source of empirical data	Predetermined options, multiple choices possible, drop down list, searchable	Field data, Plot data, Lab data, Microcosm, Farm, Catchment, Survey, Sampling Campaign, National database, Regional database, Glasshouse experiment
Comments / Clarifications	Open-ended response, text	To allow projects to expand or specify the methods used if they are not included in the previous questions.
Soil related parameters measured	Open-ended response, text	
Environmental parameters measured	Open-ended response, text	
Agronomic related parameters measured	Open-ended response, text	
Parameter Value Range	Open-ended response, text	Three text boxes to obtain a Minimum Value, Mean Value, Maximum Value
Parameter Value Units	Open-ended response, text	
Indicators used if any	Open-ended response, text	
Units of Indicators	Open-ended response, text	
Indicators are statistically valid and robust	Single answer selection from drop down list	Yes/ No
Indicators are harmonised across EU	Single answer selection from drop down list	Yes/ No

3.5. Results/ Outputs from Projects

This section aims to collect the relevant information about the outputs of the study/ research.

Table 5 Metadata required for the results section of the protocol

Input Category	Input Criteria
Format of project outputs	Open-ended response, text
Accessibility/ Availability of results	Open-ended response, text
If other, please specify	Open-ended response, text
Location where results are stored	Open-ended response, text
Links to supplementary outputs/ open data	Open-ended response, text

3.6. Relevance to the EJP SOIL

The purpose of this section is to find the relevant links between the research/ study and the various aspects of the EJP SOIL program.

Table 6 Metadata required for the EJP SOIL section of the protocol

Input Category	Input Criteria	Input Options
Relevant EJP SOIL Themes	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible, searchable	Soil carbon sequestration and climate Change Mitigation, Climate Change Adaptation, Sustainable soil management and agricultural production, Sustainable environment, soil health, ecosystem Services and biodiversity Soil data & monitoring, mapping and modelling, Region specific fertilization
Relevant EJP SOIL Targets	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible, searchable	Sustainable agricultural production, C sequestration, healthy soils, land and soil restoration, soil biodiversity, ecosystem services
Relevant EJP SOIL Expected Impacts	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible, searchable	Fostering understanding of soil management and its influence on climate mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production and environment; Understanding how soil carbon sequestration can contribute to climate change mitigation at regional level including accounting for carbon; Strengthening scientific capacities and cooperation across Europe including training of young soil scientists; Supporting harmonised European soil information, including for international reporting; Fostering the uptake of soil management practices which are conducive to climate change adaptation and mitigation;

		Developing region-specific fertilisation practices considering the local soil, water and pedo-climatic conditions;
Related EJP SOIL Projects	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible, searchable	CarboSeq, SOMMIT, TRACE-Soils, INSURE, STEROPES, SensRes, SCALE, i-SOMPE, SIREN, CLIMASOMA etc. (Fig. 7)
Relevant EJP SOIL Knowledge Framework	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible, searchable	1. Knowledge development, 2. Knowledge sharing and transfer, 3. Knowledge harmonisation, organisation and storage, 4. Knowledge application
Relevant SOIL Challenges	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible, searchable	Maintain/ Increase soil SOC, Avoid N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soil, Avoid peat degradation, Avoid soil erosion, Avoid soil sealing, Avoid salinization, Avoid acidification, Avoid contamination, Optimal soil structure, Enhance soil biodiversity, Enhance soil nutrient retention/ use efficiency, Enhance soil water storage capacity
Areas/ Topics for further research	Open-ended, text	

3.7. Relevance to Policy

Here the aim is to collect information that will be most useful to policymakers about the research/study.

Table 7 Metadata required for the policy relevance section of the protocol

Input Category	Input Criteria	Input Options
Relevant/ Targeted Stakeholders	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible, searchable	Scientific Researchers, Education, Local policymakers, National policymakers, EU policymakers, International policymakers, Interest groups, Advisory, Extension, Farmers, Other
Possible aspects of policy that can be informed	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible	Data/Evidence for policy, Monitoring, Reporting (e.g. Input on GHG emissions into IPCC), Verification, Practices (e.g. EIP best practices for soil management), Laws (E.g. Soil Health Law), Recommendations (E.g. EU Soil Strategy, Carbon Farming Initiatives), Tools(e.g. soil navigator, LANDMARK2020)
Potentially relevant policy areas	Open-ended response, text	E.g. Agricultural production, Education, Sustainability,
Possible instruments that can be informed	Predetermined responses, multiple choices possible	Market, Mandatory, voluntary, Incentives, AKIS, Regulatory, Information
Suggested policy recommendations	Open-ended response, text	E.g. To introduce new, and/or revise the existing legal framework, incentive and supporting systems
Target audience for recommendations	Open-ended response, text	E.g. EU National; Local; Regional; Category of enterprises
Specific policies that could be targeted	Open-ended response, text	E.g. Soil health Law, Green Deal, Farm to Fork, Biodiversity Strategy

4. Conclusion

This protocol for collection of research results will capture the information generated from the core work within the EJP SOIL and the associated research projects that can be used by policymakers. It is a protocol, data collection and management tool that will strengthen the bridge between science and policy by facilitating the capture, exchange and communication of key information and findings. Working closely with WP 9 has ensured that the methods used in this protocol design complement the dissemination and knowledge transfer activities within the EJP SOIL and can be further exploited in the future. The sections and questions within the protocol cover a wide range of relevant information including the project description and background as well as possible recommendations for climate smart and sustainable soil policy development and support. The formatting was designed to maximise user friendliness and ensure the capture of a good quality of information. This, like many deliverables by WP8 continues to add to supports for policymakers and to better facilitate the transfer and sharing of knowledge between the science and policy across the EJP SOIL.

5. Appendix

1 Basic project information

Project title:	XXX
Acronym:	XXX
Duration:	Dates
Topic:	XXX
Project type:	e.g. Large-sized/small-sized project
Project coordinator:	XXX, Institute
Abstract:	150-250 words giving a short overview of the project aims, methods (& key results/achievements, if available)
Key words:	Words or phrases that describe the content of the project
Key Takeaways:	1-5 simple statements that distil the main takeaway messages from the project goals targeted to a general audience.
List of project partners:	List the partners included in the project.

Figure 1 Overview section of the protocol for the collection of results

EJP SOIL Research Results Collection Protocol	
Project Co-ordinator	Response
Contact person / email :	Response
Project partners:	List partners here
Project Objectives:	List objectives here
Project website:	
Project Status:	
Project Duration	START: Please use format DD/MM/YYYY END: Please use format DD/MM/YYYY
Source of Funding:	

Figure 2 General Information section of the protocol for the collection of results

<h2 style="display: inline;">Research Results Collection Protocol</h2>			
Target Country (s):			
EU Climatic Zone (s):			
Project Scale:			
Land Use Type			
If other please specify			
Soil Type			
WRB Soil Type (Great Group)			
Please specify soil type			
USDA Soil Drainage Class			
Please specify local soil drainage class			

Figure 3 Background section of the protocol for the collection of results

EJP SOIL Research Results Collection Protocol												
Method of data collection:												
Source of empirical data:												
Soil related parameters measured:												
Parameter Value range:	Min.	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max
Parameter value units:												
Indicators used:												
Units of indicators:												
Environmental parameters measured:												
Parameter Value range:	Min.	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max
Parameter value units:												
Indicators used:												
Units of indicators:												
Agronomic related parameters measured:												
Parameter Value range:	Min.	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max	Min	Mean	Max
Parameter value units:												
Indicators used:												
Units of indicators:												
Are indicators are statistically valid and robust?												
Are indicators harmonised across the EU ?												

Figure 4 Methods section of the protocol for the collection of results

Summary of the scientific information and results related to the EJP SOIL

Expected Impacts

Project Objectives: *Short statements on the aims to be completed by the project*

Please summarize the main scientific results achieved from the project start to 31st of January and how they contribute to the 6 EJP SOIL Expected Impacts.

1. Fostering understanding of soil management and its influence on climate change mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production and environment.
2. Understanding how soil-carbon sequestration can contribute to climate change mitigation at the regional level and accounting for carbon.
3. Strengthening scientific capacities and cooperation across Europe including training young soil scientists.
4. Supporting harmonized European soil information, including for international reporting.
5. Fostering the uptake of soil management practices conducive to climate change adaptation and mitigation.
6. Develop and demonstrate region- and context-specific fertilization practices (soil, water and pedoclimatic conditions).

What was the **most surprising research result with this project** in terms of research findings: Did you achieve unexpected or unintended results? *(Please describe both positive or less positive surprise elements)*

Did **this project find new and/or unexpected opportunities to share project results and findings**: Did you achieve unexpected or unintended engagement and outreach opportunities, not originally in the project plan? *(Please describe emerging opportunities/unplanned achievements that were realized by this project, especially related to outreach/communication/engagement to share results with academic or non-academic audiences and partners.)*

If the project is ending, will the activities under this project **continue in some form**? How/What will be taken forward? Did any **new knowledge gaps** become evident during your work? Where do you see future research needs in connection with your project theme?

Max 1000 words, 2 pages.

List of project outputs

Please note that dissemination and communication activities are also reported to WP9 of the EJP SOIL by the continuous reporting template filled in by each National Coordinator/Project Coordinator.

Please, list the following outputs of the projects:

- **publications** produced by the project: peer reviewed publications and their DOI numbers, articles in journals, publications in conference proceedings or workshops, books or monographs, book chapters, theses/dissertations.
- **communication activities**: presentations and outreach workshops, seminars, videos etc.
- **new techniques**:
 - new methods/techniques established?
 - rank with existing techniques/methods: 1 - slightly improvement, 2 – improvement, 3 - significant improvement, 4 - strong improvement (e.g. high impact on reduced resources), 5 - new technique with basics/ideas from existing one, 6 - completely new technique/improvement
- **prototypes**
- **patents**
- **other outputs of the project, and links to them if possible**, e.g. trainings, software, databases etc.

Figure 5 Results section of the protocol for information capture

Relevance to EJP SOIL	Relevant Impact Areas
Please check all boxes that apply to your project.	
Relevant EJP SOIL Themes	
<input type="checkbox"/> Soil carbon sequestration and climate change mitigation	<input type="checkbox"/> Fostering understanding of soil management and its influence on climate mitigation and adaptation, sustainable agricultural production and environment <input type="checkbox"/> Climate adaptation
<input type="checkbox"/> Climate change adaptation	
<input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable soil management and agricultural production	<input type="checkbox"/> Understanding how soil carbon sequestration can contribute to climate change mitigation at regional level including accounting for carbon <input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable environment
<input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable environment, soil health, ecosystem services and biodiversity	
<input type="checkbox"/> Soil data & monitoring, mapping and modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> Strengthening scientific capacities and cooperation across Europe including training of young soil scientists
<input type="checkbox"/> Region specific fertilization	
Relevant targets	<input type="checkbox"/> Supporting harmonised European soil information, including for international reporting
<input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable agricultural production	<input type="checkbox"/> Fostering the uptake of soil management practices which are conducive to climate change adaptation and mitigation
<input type="checkbox"/> Land and soil restoration	
<input type="checkbox"/> C sequestration	<input type="checkbox"/> Developing region-specific fertilisation practices considering the local soil, water and pedo-climatic conditions
<input type="checkbox"/> Soil biodiversity	
<input type="checkbox"/> Healthy soils	
<input type="checkbox"/> Ecosystem services	

Figure 6 Relevance to the EJP SOIL themes and impact areas section of the protocol for information capture

<p>Relevant projects (your project actively interacts with)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> CarboSeq <input type="checkbox"/> SensRes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SOMMIT <input type="checkbox"/> SCALE</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> TRACE- Soils <input type="checkbox"/> i-SoMPE</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> INSURE <input type="checkbox"/> SIREN</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> STEROPES <input type="checkbox"/> CLIMASOMA</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> MIXROOT-C <input type="checkbox"/> MaxRoot-C</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> EnergyLink <input type="checkbox"/> AGROECOseqC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> ProbeField <input type="checkbox"/> Road4Schemes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SERENA <input type="checkbox"/> MINOTAUR</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SoilCompac <input type="checkbox"/> EOM4SOIL</p>		<p>Relevant projects</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SOMPACS</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <u>SoilSalAdapt</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> FREACS</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> TRUESOIL</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SICSOCDYN</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> WISH-ROOTS</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> ICONICA</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <u>CropGas</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <u>SoilSynbiotics</u></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> SOIL-HEAL</p>
<p>Describe shortly how do you interact with the other project/s?</p>			
<p>Relevant soil challenges</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Maintain/ increase SOC <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid contamination</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Avoid N2O, CH4 emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Optimal soil structure</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Avoid peat degradation <input type="checkbox"/> Enhance soil biodiversity</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Avoid soil erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Enhance soil nutrient retention/ use efficiency</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Avoid soil sealing</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Avoid salinization <input type="checkbox"/> Enhance water storage capacity</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Avoid acidification</p>			
<p>Relevant knowledge framework</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge development</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge sharing and transfer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge harmonisation, organisation and storage</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge application</p>			

Figure 7 Relevance to the EJP SOIL section of the protocol for information capture

<p>Relevant / targeted stakeholders</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Interest groups <input type="checkbox"/> Advisory <input type="checkbox"/> Extension <input type="checkbox"/> Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p>	<p>Suggested policy recommendations & their target audience</p>
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Local policymakers <input type="checkbox"/> National policymakers <input type="checkbox"/> EU policymakers <input type="checkbox"/> International policymakers</p>		<p>E.g. Indicator X developed in this project presents an opportunity to accurately measure C sequestered in the soil – National / Regional Policymakers E.g. The creation of this decision support tool that can be used to help farmers implement best practices – Extension officers/ Education</p>
<p>How were the stakeholders involved?</p>		<p>Specific policies that could be targeted</p>
<p>Aspects of policy that can be informed</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Practices (e.g. EIP best practices for soil management) <input type="checkbox"/> Laws <input type="checkbox"/> Recommendations <input type="checkbox"/> Tools (e.g. soil navigator, LANDMARK2020)</p>	<p>E.g. EU Soil Health Law, Green Deal, Farm to Fork, Biodiversity Strategy </p>
<p><input type="checkbox"/> Data/Evidence for policy <input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring <input type="checkbox"/> Reporting (e.g. Input of GHG emissions into IPCC) <input type="checkbox"/> Verification</p>		
<p>Relevant policy areas</p>		
<p>E.g. agricultural production, environmental protection, evaluating ecosystem services etc.</p>		
<p>Instruments that can be informed</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Information</p>	
<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Market <input type="checkbox"/> Mandatory <input type="checkbox"/> Voluntary <input type="checkbox"/> Incentives <input type="checkbox"/> AKIS <input type="checkbox"/> Regulatory</p>		

Figure 8 Relevance to the EJP SOIL section of the protocol for information capture

